

THE BIAS OF THE MANCHESTER PROTOCOL IN THE URGENT AND EMERGENCY CARE SECTOR

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Introduction: The Manchester protocol was created in the mid-1990s and was first applied in 1997 in the city of Manchester, England; this tool has been widely adopted to increase the quality and speed of care with a view to prioritizing the most aggravating clinical conditions. **Objective:** To analyze the challenges of implementing the Manchester protocol correctly in the urgent and emergency hospital sector and the training of the teams in this sector. **Methodology:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflective, descriptive and qualitative analysis. Ten articles from the journals Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) and Latin American and Caribbean Literature in Health Sciences (LILACS) were used. **Results (Concluded):** Throughout the use of the Manchester protocol worldwide, statistics and studies on the positive effects of this implementation have shown that: this protocol is effective and of paramount importance for the organization and planning of more effective care in urgencies and emergencies; It is also correct to affirm the importance of the protocol in reducing waiting times and improving the service provided; Studies have also been able to identify the usefulness of the protocol at the time of early identification of aggravating conditions, thus enabling a rapid start of care aimed at reducing morbidity and mortality, however, the implementation of the Manchester protocol is not without its challenges; Different studies have discussed the obstacles imposed by the training of health professionals in the assertive identification of risk classification, which can cause damage to the identification of the problem and the quality of patient care. Standardization at the time of classification and the efficient management of the resources available in the sector, which is the gateway to the emergency room, is also a challenge. **Final Considerations:** The literature on the importance of applying the Manchester protocol is noteworthy; however, it is also necessary to continue educating and training the teams that are present there on a daily basis in the emergency department; it is essential to develop the appropriate skills during the anamnesis to correctly identify the classification of the patient to be seen.

Keywords: Reception. Classification. Hospital.

Thematic Area: Reception and Risk Classification.